

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF USING ACTIVE METHODS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract

Growing material and technical needs are now ahead of the processes of social and psychological maturity of people, their ability to conduct dialogue, culture of communication, active self-knowledge and self-expression. This leads to the need to consider the meaningful processes of interaction carried out in the education system.

Keywords: education, learning, teaching methods, educational process, active learning methods, educational technologies.

Introduction. At present, an active process of modernization is taking place in the education sector of our country. The content of education is being renewed, and effective, efficient, and rational approaches to its implementation are being considered. In this regard, educators are faced with the task of continuously updating teaching methods and approaches, mastering new technologies, and learning how to apply them effectively. Therefore, the modernization of educational content has undoubtedly become a requirement of the time.

The key figure in educating an intellectually aware and enlightened generation is the teacher. The educational policy of the state is implemented through these professionals. The main objective facing the teaching community is the formation of a spiritually rich and comprehensively developed personality.

For several years, systematic measures have been implemented to improve the qualifications of university instructors and to help them master effective teaching methods. Training courses have been successfully organized at the **Orleu National Center for Professional Development** and at centers for pedagogical excellence.

During teaching practice at the higher education institution, based on the theoretical knowledge acquired during the first face-to-face stage, we first developed a short-term lesson plan. While designing the plan, we attempted to integrate group work as much as possible. This was done because our objective was to develop students' social, cognitive, and emotional spheres.

Before the beginning of the lesson and during the class, short warm-up activities were regularly conducted in order to create a positive psychological atmosphere and to focus students' attention. These activities contributed to the effectiveness of the lesson and

increased students' interest. Evidence of this can be found in the feedback provided by students in the video interview titled "*Student Voice*." Their opinions can be summarized as follows: "*We really liked the warm-up activities and game-based exercises conducted during the lesson. They improved our mood, helped us open up to each other, strengthened our friendly relationships, and increased our motivation to participate in the class.*"

Educators highly appreciate the role of group work in the learning process. In their view, group work enriches the teaching process, strengthens learning activities, and creates a warm and supportive atmosphere within the group. N.K. Krupskaya considered communication to be an essential component of pedagogical techniques that ensure the effectiveness of educational work. In 2005, the researcher Neil Mercer emphasized in his work that interaction within peer groups plays an important role in learning. According to G.M. Andreeva, communication serves as a means of uniting and developing individuals. Without communication, it is impossible to understand and analyze the process of personal development or the development of society as a whole. Psychologists also note that group work creates favorable conditions for the development and maturation of the individual [1].

Group work fosters a sense of collectivity among learners and demonstrates that collaborative activity can be engaging and meaningful. It increases students' motivation toward collective work. In real-life situations, students gradually realize that the principle of "WE" (a collective and socially oriented approach based on unity) is more beneficial than the principle of "I" (an egocentric or individualistic position). They also become convinced that this position is grounded in profound humanistic values [2].

Indeed, in our experience with group work, students demonstrated a high level of engagement and actively participated in completing the assigned tasks responsibly. They adhered to group rules and worked collaboratively, listening to one another, expressing their own ideas, and reaching shared conclusions. In addition, they attempted to identify key ideas, develop creative and critical thinking skills, strengthen internal motivation, enhance leadership abilities, and practice self-regulation. As a result, this approach significantly facilitated the effective comprehension of learning materials.

One of our students expressed the following opinion about group work in a reflective essay: *“Through group work, students participate in all aspects of the learning process: they examine their assumptions and questions, provide advice to one another, set goals, monitor outcomes, conduct experiments, and have the opportunity to correct their ideas if they are mistaken. Learning through group work becomes clearer and more memorable. Personally, I really enjoyed working in groups.”*

One of the teaching approaches that occupies an important place in effective learning programs is dialogic teaching. Since dialogue occurs between two or more individuals, it may develop in various contexts, emotional states, and conversational situations. During dialogue, students interact with each other in pairs, groups, or as a whole class. One of the main goals of education is to achieve clear understanding and to develop high-quality thinking skills. Throughout the lesson, students engage in reflection, discussion, and dialogue, which enables them to deepen their perspectives and understanding. Critical thinking encourages observation, analysis, interpretation, and the formulation of conclusions.

During classroom discussions, the primary responsibility of the instructor is not only to develop students' interest in knowledge but also to pay attention to their moral and spiritual development. For this reason, instructors themselves must continuously engage in self-development, independent learning, and the improvement of their professional knowledge.

The techniques of dialogic speech encourage students to express themselves and exchange opinions with one another. Each dialogic teaching technology creates communicative situations that stimulate students' oral communication and discussion. In this regard, A. Baitursynov noted that *“the art of constructing a beautiful narrative from words is similar to the art of building a house.”*

Language, or speech, is the primary means through which individuals express their thoughts. Language plays a fundamental role in both teaching and learning processes. In many cases, learning takes place through dialogue, and this method has been widely used, particularly in traditional forms of instruction. Scientific research has demonstrated the significant role of dialogue in the classroom. As early as 1934, Lev Vygotsky emphasized the importance of conversation for learning in his work *Thought and Language*. Similarly, Akhmet Baitursynuly stated: *“The purpose of language is to convey what the mind understands, what*

the imagination suggests, and what the heart perceives. If there is a person who can speak effectively, language can always serve its purpose. However, such a person is difficult to find.”

Communication with the instructor and with other students is an important tool that ensures students' active participation and promotes their understanding. The researcher Robin Alexander argues that teaching through dialogue provides opportunities to use the power of conversation to motivate and develop learners. According to Alexander, through dialogue teachers can identify constructive future possibilities during everyday discussions and help students work with emerging ideas while overcoming misunderstandings [3].

Early views on dialogue and its characteristics were expressed in the works of A. Baitursynuly and Q. Zhubanov. Later, the works of M. Balaqev, M. Sergaliev, and B. Shalabaev further explored the features of dialogue, particularly in relation to literary texts and stylistics [4].

During my teaching practice at a higher education institution, I applied dialogic teaching through several interactive techniques, including the Jigsaw method, “Snowball Throwing,” “Pair Work,” “Brainstorming,” and “Warm-up” activities. These methods contributed significantly to achieving the objectives set for the lesson.

The “Snowball Throwing” method was used at the beginning of the lesson as a game-based activity to review homework, recall previously learned material, and encourage peer learning and assessment. Each student received a sheet of paper and was asked to write one or two questions related to the previous topic. Afterward, the students crumpled the papers into balls resembling snowballs. Following the instructor's instructions, students threw the “snowballs” to one another. When the activity stopped, students opened the paper they had received and wrote answers to the questions. The process was repeated several times. Each student then read the question and answer written on the paper they had and analyzed whether the question was formulated correctly and whether the answer was accurate and appropriate. Only the most successful questions, the most complete and creative answers, as well as the simplest questions and incorrect answers were discussed collectively and analyzed.

The expected outcomes of this method were achieved in practice. Students recalled previous topics, exchanged opinions, and developed skills such as questioning, speaking, and listening. They also assessed each other's responses, engaged in peer evaluation, and actively participated in dialogic interaction. In addition, this method stimulated students' interest and increased their level of engagement in the lesson.

During the same lesson, while introducing the new topic, I organized a dialogic activity using the pair-work method. To help students understand the sensitivity of perception through experience, they worked in pairs. One student closed their eyes and extended both palms forward, while the other placed small pieces of torn paper into the student's palms and asked, “What did you feel?” The size of the paper pieces gradually

increased. The experiment continued until the student was able to perceive the weight of the paper placed in their hands. Afterward, the students switched roles.

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After completing the experiment, each pair discussed what they had felt and the thoughts that had arisen during the activity. Subsequently, the results were discussed within the larger group. In my opinion, such a method proved to be much more effective for students than simply listening to information presented by the instructor. It allowed students to learn more quickly and with greater interest, retain information for a longer period, and verify the results through their own experience. Moreover, the method created opportunities for students to openly express and discuss their thoughts and feelings first in pairs and then within the group.

In the following lesson, we applied the "Brainstorming" method as part of dialogic teaching in order to check homework assignments. Students sat in a circle and threw a ball to one another while asking questions related to the homework. Students who were unable to answer correctly had to come to the center of the circle and perform a short creative activity as a form of "penalty," such as demonstrating a talent or skill. As a result, students checked each other's homework, learned from one another, evaluated and corrected each other's responses. In addition, we believe that their questioning, speaking, and listening skills were significantly improved.

Another method used for dialogic teaching was the "Warm-up" activity. With the help of this method, we assessed how well students had mastered the assigned material. For this purpose, students formed two circles—an inner and an outer circle—standing opposite each other. They explained and discussed their understanding of the given topic with their partners. For example, students in the outer circle attempted to present information about temperament, while those in the inner circle shared their knowledge and understanding about character traits. During the activity, the inner and

outer circles rotated, allowing students to interact with new partners and exchange additional information. As a result, the discussion was continuously enriched with new perspectives and ideas [3].

However, the application of dialogic teaching methods during the lessons also revealed some shortcomings. One such difficulty appeared during the “Brainstorming” activity. Some students who caught the ball hesitated when asking questions. During the feedback session, the students themselves noted that their level of participation had been relatively low. They explained this by the complexity of the task and the lack of time for adequate preparation due to personal circumstances. As a result, when the ball reached them, they felt confused and unprepared. Nevertheless, plans were developed to address this issue, and additional assignments were provided to compensate for these shortcomings [4].

The selection of teaching methods usually occurs when the content of the learning material for a lesson is determined. This choice depends on several factors, including the didactic objectives of the lesson, the level of students’ knowledge, and the instructor’s own level of preparation.

While preparing short-term lesson plans, we often reflected on how dialogic teaching methods could be effectively implemented, how lessons could be successfully concluded, and whether the application of

these methods would allow us to achieve our educational objectives. Although we had previously used dialogic teaching methods, we realized that we had not always clearly defined the expected outcomes or paid sufficient attention to feedback. Therefore, in our future pedagogical practice, we plan to apply dialogic teaching methods more deeply and at a more research-oriented level, as they are considered one of the key approaches in effective teaching and learning programs.

We believe that increasing students’ interest in learning while improving the quality of education and preparing highly qualified professionals remains one of the most important responsibilities of modern higher education.

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